

An updated review on-Heat Stress imbalance and enhancement of wheat

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Abstract— Wheat is a crucial cereal crop and is considered a source of fundamental calories and protein for more than 80% of the world's population. The impact of increasing temperatures on wheat production has been a global concern over the past few decades owing to global climate change. Heat is the major a-biotic stress limiting wheat production. Heat stress disrupts important morphological, physiological and biochemical, molecular processes in the plant. High temperature stress reduces plant height, grain number, photosynthetic activity, starch synthesis in the endosperm. Reactive oxygen species accumulate under heat stress and can cause severe oxidative damage to crops. Plants rapidly produce heat shock proteins to reduce the effects of heat stress. Numerous traits, such as stay green, chlorophyll fluorescence, and canopy temperature, play a significant role in heat tolerance. Knowledge of the effects of heat stress and tolerance at the physiological, biochemical, and morphological, molecular levels is crucial for developing new crop varieties that can crop with future climates.

Keywords— Wheat, Heat stress, Oxidative stress, Heat shock proteins

I. INTRODUCTION

Wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) is one of the world's primary food crops, covering more land under cultivation than any other food crop on the planet. With reference to 1/3rd of the world's population depends on it for food and nutrition. Both climate change and the growing world population pose threats to food security [1]. Climate change results in more extreme temperatures due to reduced rainfall, changing rainfall patterns and distribution, and shorter winters. The most detrimental abiotic stresses like drought and heat for the growth and development of crop plants, affecting yield and the final quality of food products [2].

According to global climate models, average ambient temperatures are projected to increase by 1.5°C within the next two decades [3] and crop plants will be exposed to heat stress. Wheat is one of the most important cereal crops grown worldwide in terms of cultivated area and contributes significantly to global cereal production (28%) and trade (41.5%) [4]. Despite being the world's second largest wheat producer, India's average yield is only 2770 kg/ha compared to China's 3885 kg and the UK, Netherlands and other NW European countries' 8043 kg. High temperatures, particularly during grain filling, short cropping season and short grain filling period are the reasons for the low yield in India [5]. Persistent heat stress (mean daily temperature in the coldest month of the season 17.5°C) affects approximately 7 million hectares of wheat in developing countries, while terminal heat stress is a problem in 40% of temperate environments, which account for 36 million hectares [6]. Like other C3 species, wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) is physiologically unsuited to thrive in hot environments, especially during the grain filling stage. According to [7], a 1°C increase in temperature during grain filling proportionally reduces the harvest index and grain yield of wheat and shortens this period by 5%. The effects of heat stress on reducing photosynthesis, affecting respiration, inactivating enzymes and degrading membranes can significantly reduce biomass production [8,9].

Wheat is a major winter food grain worldwide. The adverse effects of climate change on wheat production pose a threat to global food security, and sustained wheat production is expected to be negatively affected by rising global temperatures [10]. Heat stress has a negative impact on wheat production in different parts of the world. It is particularly detrimental during the reproductive stage of the wheat plant [11]. The impacts of heat stress and potential mechanisms to improve heat tolerance for wheat production in the heat are important to recognize due to global warming and changes in extreme weather conditions. Because heat stress and potential mechanisms has to improve heat tolerance are directly related to the profitability

of wheat production in the heat. Production and other yield attributes of wheat are greatly affected by high heat conditions [12]. Generally low-elevation regions have large areas of wheat cultivation, and these crops are often heat sensitive [13]. Research with various models for average temperature revealed a significant decrease in wheat yield at higher temperatures. Elevated temperature results in changes in germination, stem growth, root emergence, tillering, root growth, dry matter production, panicle vigor, seed characteristics, fertilization and pollination [14].

Wheat is very sensitive to heat stress. A 1°C increase in temperature is estimated to reduce global wheat production by 6% [15]. Even a 1°C increase in temperature above the average temperature during the reproductive phase can cause a significant loss in grain yield [16,17]. High temperature alters various physiological, biological and biochemical processes in wheat [18,19]. Heat stress (HS) in wheat results in poor seed germination, reduced grain filling period, decrease grain number, inactivation of Rubisco enzyme, reduced photosynthetic efficiency, reduction assimilate translocation rate, senescence of leaves, reduced chlorophyll content and ultimately reduced yield [20-25]. HS also affects the starch and protein content of the grain. HS stimulate the production of reactive oxygen species (ROS) that cause changes in membrane stability with lipid peroxidation, protein oxidation and damage to nucleic acids [26,27]. Although, to avoid the injury and damage associated with HS, wheat has developed various tolerance mechanisms to maintain its survival and growth. HS-induced heat shock proteins (HSPs) maintain proper protein folding, refolding, synthesis, and it degrades protein synthesis [28,29]. Accumulated ROS are detoxified by the antioxidant defense system through different enzymatic and non-enzymatic antioxidants [30-36]. The present review covers the effect of HS on wheat morphology, physiology and biochemistry, and Molecular techniques. Furthermore, we elucidated various HS tolerance mechanisms and SG traits associated with heat tolerance, such as the oxidative defence system and the production of HS-induced HSPs.

Consequence of Heat stress on wheat

High temperature disrupts the morphology, physiology and biochemistry of wheat crops, which ultimately leads to reduced grain filling, photosynthetic activities, chlorophyll levels and starch synthesis [37]. At severe high temperatures (heat stress), yields are reduced by 6 to 51% [38]. Heat stress also affects double shoot stage and growth of shoots and roots, and early biomass at the vegetative stage [39]. An increase in global temperature has led to reduced photosynthetic efficiency and crop yields. High day-night temperatures severely affect grain number, seed set and grain yield per spike [40].

Consequence of Heat stress on Vegetative stage

Life cycle proceedings of wheat plants are highly responsive to heat shock. Poor establishment is a result of high soil temperatures, which reduced healthy wheat germination and also affect plant growth and shoot biomass accumulation. High temperatures inhibit the photosynthetic machinery by shortening the vegetative period, reducing tillering, increasing oxidative stress, and increasing flowering progress. High temperatures have a through impact on the photosynthetic apparatus of wheat and other cereal crops, reduce photosynthesis, photoassimilate formation, and shoot biomass fabrication throughout the vegetative process [41]. The level of damage will be determined by the growth stage at which the wheat plants are subjected to temperature extremes. Subsequent to 7 days of germination, heat treatment at 45°C for 2 h reduced shoot and root length, dry mass, chlorophyll content and membrane stability index [42]. Heat treatment at 42°C for 24 hours prevented the growth of roots and first leaves; this resulted in upraised of reactive oxygen species and lipid peroxidation products in developing coleoptile and seedling stage organs [43].

Physiological effect on wheat

The water content of the plant changes very irregularly when the temperature keeps changing. As the temperature increases, the plant tissues face dehydration, which delays the growth and development of the plants. 31°C is considered as the maximum limit, which maintains the water content of the crops at the flowering stage. Research by Almeselmani, Deshmukh, and Chinnusamy (2012) [44] showed that when

the temperature is high after tillage (from about 35 to 25°C), the water capacity in wheat decreases and the reduction is more in genotypes that are more susceptible to heat stress. Dehydration tolerance is associated with different antioxidants, which are induced as a result of increased transpiration and decreased osmotic capacity in the leaf induced during heat stress. Furthermore, heat stress reduces water viscosity and increases hydraulic conductivity in cell membranes and plant tissues[45].

Speaking of photosynthetic tissues, photosystem II is the most sensitive to heat stress and photosystem I is the most stable. First, the complex process of photosystem II is damaged and second, the photosynthetic behavior is altered by heat stress. Rubisco activase is inactivated and carbon assimilation is suppressed. As a result, protein synthesis is reduced and photosystem II is unable to compensate for its damage[46].

The most important physiological event responsible for the poor growth of wheat is photosynthesis. This results in reduced leaf area, defective photosynthetic machinery, premature leaf death and eventual reduction in wheat yield[47]. The stroma, thylakoid lamellae of chloroplasts, is the main sites of heat stress injury due to the disruption of carbon metabolism. This disrupts the enzyme-related activities and disrupts electron carriers leading to a lower photosynthetic rate [48]. When wheat leaves are exposed to temperatures above 40°C in the dark or in the light, a change occurs in Rubisco and Rubisco activase, which is irreversible in the dark[49]. Leaf senescence is an inevitable consequence of heat stress, the symptoms of which are structural changes in chloroplasts, collapse of vacuoles, loss of integral plasma membrane and interference with cellular homeostasis. Flag leaf senescence in wheat was observed to be more severe when there was a large variation in daily temperature[50]. Leaf senescence was another the unavoidable outcome of heat stress whose symptoms are structural alteration in the chloroplast, collapse of vacuole, loss of integrated plasma membrane and interference in homeostasis of cells. Flag leaf senescence in wheat was seen more when there occurs large variation in diurnal temperature[50].

Respiration effect on heat stress

The effect of heat stress on respiration is not well understood. As temperatures rise, the cost of respiration in plants also increases and eventually the rate of photosynthesis reaches a point where it is no longer possible to keep up with the energy demand[51]. At this point, respiratory losses become too great for the plant to compensate, leading to a reduction in growth and overall health. In simple terms, as temperatures rise, plants have to work harder to maintain their functions, and if this cost is too high, it will negatively affect their growth. This can be compared to a person who has to work harder to maintain their health in hot weather, and if this becomes too demanding, they will eventually become exhausted and tired. High-temperature stress stimulates mitochondrial production of oxygen radicals, and these organs respond to stress tolerance by producing distinct stress-resistant proteins[52]. The combined effect of drought and high temperature altered the mitochondrial ultrastructure of leaves of susceptible wheat varieties [53].

Stomatal conductance

When the temperature difference between the inside and outside of a plant is high, the plant can better regulate its temperature by allowing water to evaporate through its stomata. Evaporative cooling is a process that helps lower the temperature within the plant's canopy, which helps protect the plant from the negative effects of heat stress. When the temperature is high everywhere else around, the plant cools itself by evaporating water vapor through its stomata. This effectively lowers the temperature within the plant's canopy. This phenomenon is called "canopy temperature depression (CTD)," which describes this drop in temperature. Along the utilizing evaporative cooling across stomatal conductance, plants are better equipped to cope with high temperatures and keep optimal growing conditions. There is a strong correlation between CTD and wheat stomatal conductance in hot environments[54,55]. Stomatal conductance has been proposed as a useful selection criterion for wheat yield under heat stress and has high heritability [55,56]. The vapor pressure deficit between the canopy and the atmosphere and the chemical signals generated in dehydrated roots regulate stomatal opening/closing, thus maintaining the water potential of the plant [58].

Biochemical tolerance mechanisms

Ribulose-1,5-bisphosphate carboxylase oxygenase activase (RCA) plays an important role in the acclimatization to various abiotic stresses[59]. TaHsfC2a-B functions as a transcriptional activator that activates genes related to heat protection. It plays a crucial role in proactively safeguarding the developing wheat grains from heat stress by engaging in the ABA-mediated regulatory pathway [60]. A series of HS genes and a few QTLs accountable for plant growth under stress conditions can protect plants from stress conditions [61]. Thermotolerance in crops can be increased by the accumulation of several compounds with lower molecular weights known as thermo-protectants or phytohormones[62].

Membrane stability

Membrane thermostability is a valuable trait for selecting heat-tolerant wheat genotypes [63]. There is a high genetic variation and heritability for membrane stability in wheat [64,65]. Heat stress damage the plasma membrane and leads to leakage of solutes. The extent of heat damage depends on the degree of saturation of lipids in the membrane. A set of different wheat lines for cell membrane stability (CTS) was assessed under heat stress conditions and CTS can effectively discriminate between heat-tolerant and susceptible lines and shows significant correlation with yield[66]. Increased membrane stability index at elevated temperatures was observed in heat-tolerant wheat genotypes owing to increased antioxidant enzyme activity [67]. Plants that can preserve their high-temperature membrane function are more tolerant to heat stress[68]

Anti-oxidant defence

Environmental stress causes the accumulation of ROS, which are found in the subcellular compartment causing acute damage to crops, and the toxicity of ROS is attenuated by enzymatic and non-enzymatic antioxidants[69]. Different antioxidants play an important role in the antioxidant defense mechanisms as shown in Table 1. The increase in the absorption of light energy leads to potentially scavenging reactions, including the production of ROS [75]. Since cell signaling between chloroplast and nucleus plays a crucial role in crop survival from stress, efficient communication between plastids and nucleus is required to cope with heat stress[76]. Methyl Jasmonate (MeJA) can help prevent heat stress in wheat crops by protecting PS II and D1 proteins and restoring photosynthetic capacity[77]. Application of both sodium nitroprusside (SNP) and gibberellic acid after 10 DAS resulted in significant increases in plant height (4.48%), plant fresh weight (29.7%), dry weight (87%), photosynthetic rate (39.76%), stomatal conductance (38.10%) and RuBisCO(54.2%) [78]. Plant antioxidant defense systems include enzymatic components such as ascorbate glutathione reductase, peroxidase, polyphenol oxidase, peroxidase, catalase, and superoxide dismutase, along with non-enzymatic components such as carotenes, ascorbic acid, and α -tocopherol. Antioxidants activated by stress detection protect against oxidative damage and cellular integrity [79]. Application of AgNP to wheat helps in thermotolerance in wheat [80](Iqbal et al., 2019). Application of selenium increases enzymatic and non-enzymatic antioxidants and reduces oxidative stress induced by heat stress [81](Iqbal et al., 2015). Melatonin can help increase stress tolerance in wheat crops by accelerating the antioxidant defense mechanism and regulating the stress response gene [82]. Melatonin helps detoxify reaction byproducts, promotes physiological functions, regulates plant hormones, and increases protein homeostasis to enhance heat stress defense mechanisms. In addition, melatonin increases the unfolded protein response, endoplasmic reticulum-associated degradation, and autophagy, which safeguard cells from programmed cell death and promote cell repair, thereby improving plant survival [83]. Increased expression of the wheat ferritin gene, TaFER-5B, plays an essential role in enhancing heat stress tolerance and ROS scavenging [84]. The decreased rate of relative water content, slower chlorophyll degradation, increased proline content, and higher membrane stability may enhance heat tolerance in wheat[85]. Reactive oxygen species such as singlet oxygen, superoxide, and hydroxyl radicals are produced in plants during heat stress, which alters the balance between the generation and scavenging of ROS in normal cells [86]. Owing to increased ROS production, enzymes related to free radical scavenging are induced, which in turn stimulates the antioxidant defense system [87]. The

production of antioxidant enzymes such as CAT, POX and SOD activity increases under different levels of stress [88]. The catalytic activity of SOD decrease metal ions in the cell [89]. Hydroxyl radicals ($\bullet\text{OH}$) can be neutralized by scavenging hydrogen peroxide across the action of peroxidases such as guaiacol peroxidase, ascorbate peroxidase (APX) or catalase (CAT) [90]. Although oxidative stress and ROS production are linked, reactive oxygen species (ROS) can also act as signaling molecules under different abiotic conditions, increasing resistance[91]. In summary, understanding the dynamics of ROS synthesis and antioxidant defense mechanisms will help develop strategies to improve plant defense against various stresses.

TABLE 1. Various role of antioxidants in scavenging Reactive Oxygen Species.

Antioxidant	Functions	Reference
Enzymatic antioxidants		
APX	Removing hydrogen peroxide by oxidizing ascorbate.	[70]
GPX	Facilitates the decomposition of hydrogen peroxide.	[71]
CAT	Transform H_2O_2 into oxygen and water without employing any reducing agents.	[72]
SOD	Facilitates the conversion of superoxide radicals into hydrogen peroxide and oxygen.	[73]
Non Enzymatic antioxidants		
Tocopherol	Substances that remove hydrogen peroxide; increase in the expression of glutathione reductase (GR) and ascorbate peroxidase (APX).	[74]
Ascorbic acid	Contribute electrons in several non-enzymatic and enzymatic reactions.	[70]
Glutathione	Agents that eliminate singlet oxygen, hydrogen peroxide, and hydroxyl radicals.	[71]
Carotenoids	Prevent the synthesis of singlet oxygen.	[70]

Molecular tolerance mechanisms

Heat shock protein

Under high-temperature stress, plants detect and express this stimulus, which leads to physiological, biochemical, and genetic responses, including oxidative stress, which affects reactive oxygen species (ROS) production, macromolecule, and nucleic acid synthesis; as a result, heat shock proteins (HSPs) play a key role by protecting cell membrane integrity, scavenging ROS, and producing antioxidants and osmolytes. Plants have inherent molecular-level mechanisms to tolerate or avoid extreme heat conditions. Heat shock proteins are a group of proteins that are synthesized in response to heat stress and are regulated by transcription factors[92]. Understanding the function of HSPs in response to heat stress requires considering their association with membranes, as approximately two-thirds of chloroplast HSPs translocate to thylakoid membranes during heat stress [93]. Different heat shock proteins have various roles in heat stress tolerance, As exhibit in Table 2.

TABLE 2. Role of different heat shock proteins under heat stress.

Heat Shock Proteins	Functions	Reference
Small HSPs	Assists in refolding of denatured proteins, thereby preventing thermal aggregation of denaturing proteins.	[94,95]
HSP40	After synthesis of completely refolded protein involved in the refolding which are released by HSP70, HSP40. HSP100.	[96]
HSP60	Assists in Protein refolding and stopping the collection of denatured protein.	[73]
HSP70	Helps in the accurate folding of protein and stabilization of recently formed protein by controlling aggregate synthesis.	[97]
HSP90	Conciliate HS linked signal transduction and promotes CO ₂ assimilation rate and kernel weight.	[98,99]
HSP100	Disintegration of protein aggregate which is ATP controlled process.	[73]

During plant growth of wheat crops, proteins in the cytosol and endoplasmic reticulum (ER) are exposed to heat stress, which is facilitated by regulatory mechanisms controlled by reactive oxygen species (ROS) [76]. This coincides with the development of heat shock proteins (HSPs) during the grain filling and maturation stage, as the wheat embryo experiences an increase in abscisic acid (ABA) content[100]. The cellular machinery relies heavily on proper protein synthesis and folding; however, under high stress conditions, this process is disrupted, leading to significant impacts on cell function by misfolded proteins, with heat shock protein 70 attracting worldwide attention for its plant biological interactions[101]. The key function occurs at 40C and heat shock proteins are to protect seedlings from death caused by heat shock[102]. Many plants contain heat shock transcription factors (Hsfs), which play a key role in thermotolerance, transgenerational thermomemory and different stress responses[103]. Overexpression of heat shock factor subunit C (TaHsfC2a-B) significantly increased the survival of heat-stressed wheat seedlings[104]. TaHsfA6f is a transcriptional activator that directly regulates the TaGAAP, TaHSP and TaRof1 genes in wheat and its gene regulatory network has a positive effect on thermotolerance[100,105]. Small heat shock proteins (sHSPs) are broadly known for their capability to act as molecular chaperones in the laboratory setting, preventing the aggregation of sensitive proteins when exposed to high temperatures. The TaHsfA6b-4D protein plays a key role in coordinating heat stress responses, by translocating within the cell during heat stress, helping to maintain homeostasis[106]. Overexpression of the TaHsfA6b protein helps to improve the growth, development, and survival of wheat plants[107]. Therefore, TaHsfA6b plays a vital role in coordinating the cytosolic HSR with the ER-UPR, which appears to be key steps in the thermo-sensing process.

HEAT TOLERANCE MECHANISM IN WHEAT

Plants have various adaptive mechanisms to adapt under HS. Avoidance, Escape, and Tolerance are the three main mechanisms that permit plants to survive and grow in high temperature environments. Heat

tolerance is defined as the ability of plants to survive, grow and produce economic yields under HS. The formation of antioxidant defenses and creation of heat shock proteins (HSPs) are the main heat tolerance mechanisms in wheat.

Adoption of sustainable farming practices

Global policies encourage the adoption of sustainable agricultural practices, such as conservation tillage and cover cropping, to help mitigate the effects of heat stress on wheat crops. Adopting sustainable agricultural practices can help mitigate the effects of heat stress on crops and improve their resilience to high temperatures. SG is an important mechanism for HS tolerance in wheat because it preserves the photosynthetic area and increases nitrogen fixation to the maturing grains [108]. The Stay Green (SG) associated genotype maintains photosynthesis and grain filling in HS conditions [109]. During the stages of ovary development, starch content in the ovary decreases rapidly, but under HS, sugar accumulation decreases owing to reduced photosynthetic activity, which contributes to seed abortion [109]. The increased photosynthetic activity owing to SG helps maintain a continuous supply of sugar in the developing anther and pollen, thus helping to maintain the viability of pollen and ovules [110]. A study was conducted to correlate SG traits with canopy temperature depression (CTD) [111]. They found a higher value of CTD (air temperature-canopy temperature) in SG genotypes under HS condition and concluded that SG is highly correlated with CTD. Thus, SG trait can be used as a selection criterion under heat stress in wheat genotypes [112].

Research and development

There is notable emphasis on conducting research aimed at understanding the mechanisms underlying heat tolerance in wheat and developing new breeding strategies to ameliorate heat tolerance of wheat crops. Investments are being made in biotechnology to develop new technologies for breeding and genetic engineering of heat-tolerant wheat. This comprises the development of new tools for gene editing and the use of molecular markers to track the inheritance of heat-tolerant genes. The integration of new technologies such as precision breeding, genetic selection and phenotyping is playing an increasingly vital role in the development of heat-tolerant wheat varieties. These technologies allow for the rapid and efficient evaluation of large numbers of wheat varieties, thus enabling the identification of those with higher levels of heat tolerance.

CONCLUSION

Global warming has seriously affected crop growth, leading to reduced yields of different crops, including wheat crops. At different stages, the reproductive stages of wheat crops are severely affected. At grain filling stages, heat stress has led to shrinkage of seeds and decreased individual kernel weight. To decrease the efficacy of heat stress, wheat crops have developed different tolerances that help protect against heat stress. The main tolerance mechanism involves morphological, physiological, biochemical and molecular mechanisms to reduce heat. Our study will help the researcher understand the diverse effects of heat stress and proceed towards to counter heat stress, which will help in developing heat stress tolerant varieties. Our findings contribute to a deeper understanding of heat stress and will be useful for plant breeders and farmers to understand and apply in their field. This review only provides a valuable overview of current research on the effects of heat stress on wheat and outlines possible avenues for future research.

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